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Abstract: The concept of competitiveness is applied to various subjects of economic activity, in particular, small business subjects or sectors, countries, as well as individual goods produced. Therefore, the analysis of the problem of competitiveness can be approached at different levels - at the macro level (at the level of the entire economy), at the level of the industry, at the level of the sector or at the level of clusters, small business entities and individual goods. The tiered approach suggests using a certain set of indicators for each tier of analysis and making comparisons based on them.

Keywords: small business, indicators, quality and price.

When forming a system of indicators describing the competitiveness of a product, the combination of quality and price characteristics that ensure satisfaction of the needs of a specific customer is taken into account. Competitor is understood as goods whose set of consumer and cost characteristics determines its success in the market, that is, the ability of this product to be sold on the market in the conditions of a significant offer for the sale of other competing analog goods. Currently, goods with unique consumer characteristics that do not have competing analogues have the highest level of competitiveness.

The competitiveness of goods is a synthetic indicator that reflects the result of many factors, namely, the efficiency of the work of designers, the production activity of the enterprise and its subcontractors, and the work of marketing organizations in

the sale of goods on the market. But the competitiveness of a product in a competitive market is not only its high quality and technical level. It is a skillful promotion of goods in the market space, the most important thing is to take maximum account of market requirements and specific groups of consumers. A product manufacturer must respond flexibly to market conditions, customer requirements, and competitor behavior. The goods received by the market should not only be produced in the required quantity and delivered to the sellers and buyers on time, but also the level of such service should be ensured, which is formed in the world practice.

Economic competition between countries has intensified in the last few decades. Most every country strives to become an influential and important participant in international economic relations and to take a decent place in the world economic market in order to prevent the main risks caused by globalization. Although there are doubts that states/nations are still competing, this remains the case. When the market is open, not only businesses, but also countries compete.

Since entrepreneurship is possible only under certain governance conditions, at the macro level we have evidence of competition between states for investment, oil, environment and "green technology" resources. The experience of the global economic crisis has shown that the countries most vulnerable to external influences are countries with a low level of national competitiveness. Therefore, the topic of competitiveness is very relevant and important for the future development of any country.

Currently, there is no single approach to interpreting national competitiveness as a concept and determining its place in other main economic categories. This issue has now become the subject of foreign and local scientific research. The purpose of the study is to reveal and compare different approaches to determining national competitiveness as a complex, contradictory economic category.

The main reason for the multiplicity of definitions of national competitiveness is the complexity of the term; its composite character; moreover, the concept of the

category itself is the framework of the system. Competitiveness is a complex multidimensional concept. It reflects the favorable position of the national economy, mainly in the field of international trade, and at the same time, the ability to strengthen this position. On the other hand, the competitiveness of the national economy is the aggregate expression of economic, scientific and technical, organizational, management, marketing and other capabilities implemented in goods and services, which successfully insures their competitive opposite foreign goods and services in the domestic market.

National competitiveness is the state's ability to achieve high rates of economic growth, to ensure stable growth of real wages, to create new jobs in the future, and to promote local firms represented by high-performance clusters in the world market. This competitive ability to adapt to changes in the world market is based on investment volume, innovation capacity, production capacity and other economic factors. However, their indicators should be combined with political and social factors that also affect the performance of the national economy in the world market. Analysis of the economic development of world countries through the prism of national competitiveness made it possible to develop the following models of increasing national competitiveness (Picture 1).

Picture 1. Models of national competitiveness improvement

Thus, the same steps can be applied to review and assess the national competitiveness of any country. The issues of determining the level of competitiveness of the national economy and developing measures to improve it became especially relevant after the global financial and economic crisis caused fundamental changes in the dynamics of the world economy and the economic development of large countries. The changes that took place, respectively, had a significant impact on the level and competitiveness of many countries of the world, as a result of which there were significant changes in the ratings compiled by this indicator.

Currently, most of the countries of the world are trying to solve the problems of studying which economies will occupy the first places in the competitiveness ranking in the future and which ways of increasing competitiveness will be more effective for this or that economy in changing conditions. Thus, in a situation where there is no common opinion about the future path of world development after the emergency, each country should develop a strategy to increase national competitiveness in this uncertain future.

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